

Section of the conference: Educational sciences | Sekcja konferencji: Nauki o wychowaniu

How to cite: Virella, P. (2025). Beyond the Human: Posthumanism, Inclusion and the Migrant Classroom. *International Conference on Next-Generation Innovations and Sustainability 2025*. Futurity Research Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15051742>

Beyond the Human: Posthumanism, Inclusion and the Migrant Classroom

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Accepted: March 6, 2025 | **Published:** March 19, 2025 | **Language:** English

Abstract: This paper explores the concept of inclusive classrooms in a polycrisis or crisis-stricken world through a post-human lens by analyzing 500 photographs collected in Saltier Public Schools (SPS), a district known for its diverse linguistic and migrant populations. I use a post-human perspective to challenge anthropocentric biases, advocating for classrooms to consider the needs and perspectives of all beings, technologies, and environments. Findings highlight the importance of adaptability, technology integration, and community engagement, fostering inclusive spaces that support diverse learners in the face of global crises and ultimately addressing disparities faced by migrant students across the globe.

Keywords: posthumanism, polycrisis, migration, inclusive schools

Introduction

Recent years have witnessed an unprecedented convergence of crises, impacting all facets of life, particularly affecting education (Virella, 2025). Scholars and leaders worldwide now recognize this interconnected web of challenges as a "polycrisis," a term that describes the simultaneous occurrence of multiple catastrophic events (UNICEF, 2023). This necessitates re-evaluating the educational model and searching for innovative approaches to serve diverse student populations better in turbulent times. Previous research has shown that migrant students often face significant barriers to education, including language barriers, cultural integration challenges, and trauma (Suárez-Orozco & Suárez-

Orozco, 2019). However, these studies often focus on human-centered solutions and may overlook the role of non-human actors in creating inclusive environments. Therefore, this paper addresses this gap and explores the potential of post-humanism to inform the design and implementation of inclusive classrooms within a school district facing these very challenges. Post-humanism is defined as recognizing that education is not simply the efficient delivery of knowledge (Freire, 1970) but rather a relational process involving human and non-human actors, technologies, and environments (Blaikie, Daigle, & Vasseur, 2020). By employing a post-human lens to analyze visual data collected from Saltier Public Schools, a diverse, urban school district in the Northeastern United States, this study seeks to identify strategies for fostering inclusive learning environments that address the complexities of the polycrisis, concurrently supporting the needs of all learners, particularly migrant students. This research seeks to move beyond traditional, human-centered approaches to education to include human and non-human actors such as technology (AI usage, interactive pedagogies), fostering a classroom where these concepts can coincide to create an inclusive environment. Posthumanism offers a compelling theoretical framework for rethinking inclusion by challenging human exceptionalism and recognizing the agency of non-human actors such as technologies, materials, and environments (Barad, 2007; Wolfe, 2010). It calls for an expanded understanding of learning as situated within a dynamic network of relationships that transcend human-centered interactions (Taylor, 2018). From this perspective, inclusive education is not merely about accommodating differences but about fundamentally reimagining the relationality between students, teachers, technologies, and the material world. For example, posthumanism encourages educators to view classroom tools—such as whiteboards or digital platforms—not just as passive objects but as active participants in shaping learning experiences (Yan, Litts & Na, 2020). This is especially relevant in classrooms serving migrant populations, where technology and other resources can play a crucial role in bridging language barriers, providing access to information, and fostering a sense of belonging. Building on this, Blaikie, Daigle, and Vasseur (2020) propose that a posthumanist approach necessitates dismantling traditional power structures in education, repositioning teachers and learners as co-creators of knowledge, and valuing diverse ways of knowing beyond the intellect.

By decentering the human and embracing an ecology of interdependent relations (Taylor, 2018), posthumanism aligns closely with critical pedagogy and social justice education. Both frameworks seek to disrupt power hierarchies and promote equity by valuing diverse ways of knowing and being. Posthumanism extends this commitment by emphasizing the ethical responsibilities educators have toward non-human entities and environments within educational spaces (Naraian, 2021). This shift broadens our understanding of what it means to create truly inclusive learning environments—ones that recognize the interconnectedness of all actors and challenge traditional notions of agency and inclusion. By incorporating and evaluating post-human elements, we can move towards classrooms that not only accommodate migrant students but also empower them by recognizing the agency and contributions of all actors, human and non-human, within the learning environment. This paper will proceed by first reviewing the literature on inclusive education and post-humanism, then presenting a visual analysis of classrooms in Saltier Public School District, and finally

discussing the implications of these findings for creating more equitable learning environments for migrant students.

Research Aim and Research Questions

The purpose of this paper is to explore the potential of post-humanism to inform more inclusive classroom environments that support migrant students amidst a state of polycrisis. Recognizing that migration often disrupts traditional learning environments and challenges existing notions of inclusion, this study investigates how a post-human lens can contribute to creating more inclusive educational spaces. Moreover, this research directly responds to Naraian's (2021) call for education to actively challenge the power dynamics that shape inclusion and exclusion, rather than simply accommodating differences. Thus, through the analysis of visual data to identify elements of an inclusive learning environments. To guide this exploration, the research addresses the following questions:

- How, if at all, can a post-human perspective illuminate the specific needs of migrant students?
- What role can technology, classroom design and other non-human elements play in fostering inclusive classroom environments for migrant students?

This study employs a qualitative visual analysis (Lorimer, 2013) to explore post-humanism's potential to inform inclusive classrooms for migrant students in Saltier Public Schools District. Five hundred photographs representing diverse grade levels, subjects, and classroom configurations were collected from district classrooms (September 2023 - June 2025) with consent from teachers and administrators. A post-human coding scheme, informed by Blaikie, Daigle, and Vasseur (2020), guided the analysis, moving beyond human-centered approaches to recognize non-human agency and challenge anthropocentric biases. Coding categories included technology integration, classroom layout, representations of diversity, student agency, human-nonhuman interaction, accessibility, and multilingualism; practices that align with post-humanist notions of decentering the teacher and empowering students as co-creators of knowledge (Blaikie, Daigle, & Vasseur, 2020). I coded each photograph, and data was analyzed to identify recurring themes and contradictions related to inclusivity for migrating students.

Research Results

The following section briefly describes five emergent themes resulting from analyzing 500 photographs taken across Saltier Public Schools. Overall, the context of polycrisis—marked by intersecting challenges such as migration, pandemics, and systemic inequities—calls for a radical rethinking of inclusion not evident in Saltier Public Schools. Firstly, the findings suggest that current educational practices are ill-equipped to address these complexities because they remain rooted in static models of inclusion that prioritize efficiency over relationality. For example, the data revealed that traditional, human-centered approaches to inclusion, such as worksheet-driven activities (Figure 1) and limited technology use, fail to address the complexities of diverse classroom environments fully. Out of 500 photographs, technology was present in 20% of classrooms (e.g., Promethean boards, Chromebooks). However, interactive use was observed in only 10% of cases (Figure 2).

Secondly, while technology such as Promethean boards is present in some classrooms, its use is often passive rather than interactive or transformative. These findings highlight missed opportunities to leverage inclusive technologies—such as adaptive tools, multilingual platforms, and AI-driven personalization—to bridge gaps for migrant students and those with disabilities. Thirdly, multilingual labels and cultural artifacts (Figure 3) in some classrooms demonstrate an awareness of diversity but often lack depth or meaningful integration into pedagogical practices. Representations of diversity (e.g., posters, multilingual materials) were present in 15% of classrooms but often lacked depth or integration into pedagogy. Additionally, multilingual materials were present in 22% of classrooms, primarily reflecting Spanish and Arabic languages (Figure 4). Fourthly, findings show minimal evidence of meaningful interactions between students and non-human elements (e.g., natural materials and technology). Fifthly and finally, evidence of student agency was found in 25% of classrooms, primarily tied to structured activities like textbook activities (Figure 5) rather than open-ended, inquiry-based learning. Open-ended or inquiry-based tasks were rare (Figure 6). This suggests that current practices often reinforce teacher-centered dynamics rather than empower students as knowledge co-creators. Importantly, interactions between humans and non-human elements (e.g., natural materials, interactive technologies) were observed in only 10% of classrooms. This limited engagement underscores the need for a shift in educational practices toward relationality and interconnectedness. A posthumanist perspective emphasizes decentering the teacher as the sole authority and fostering collective agency among students, teachers, technologies, and other non-human actors. Posthumanism challenges educators to move beyond tokenistic representations of diversity by embedding it into the material-discursive arrangements of classrooms—where materials and practices actively co-produce inclusive learning environments. The findings suggest that overall, the learning environments in Saltier Public School District fail to provide a holistic ecosystem with posthuman elements necessary to support migrant students navigating displacement and crisis.

Conclusions

This paper has explored the potential of posthumanism to inform inclusive education for migrant students amidst a polycrisis. Through a visual analysis of classrooms in Saltier Public School District, the study identified several key areas for improvement, including technology integration, representation of diversity, student agency, and human-nonhuman interactions. While current practices often fall short of posthuman ideals, the findings highlight the transformative potential of decentering the teacher, fostering relationality, and embracing diversity as a strength. As schools grapple with the complex challenges of migration and inequality, future research should focus on developing and evaluating posthuman pedagogies that promote equity, agency, and belonging for all students.

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Figure 1
Worksheet Driven Learning

Figure 2
Interactive Usage in Classrooms

Figure 3
Multilingual Labels in Classroom

Figure 4
Evidence of Arabic and Spanish Visual Aids

Figure 5
Textbook Driven Activity

Figure 6
Inquiry-Based Activity

